

Development of A Socio-Scientific Issues (SSI)-Based E-Module on Human Growth and Development to Improve Senior High School Students' Critical Thinking and Scientific Literacy

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ABSTRACT: This research aimed to develop and validate a Socio-Scientific Issues (SSI)-based Biology e-module on the topic of human growth and development and to examine its effectiveness in enhancing students' critical thinking and scientific literacy. The study employed the 4-D development model, including define, design, develop, and disseminate stages. Product validation involved material experts, media experts, instrument experts, and Biology teachers. The module was tested through limited trials and field trials using a pretest– posttest control group design. Critical thinking skills were assessed through essay tests based on Facione's indicators, while scientific literacy was measured using PISA-based multiple-choice tests. The e-module achieved excellent feasibility in terms of content, media quality, practicality, and readability, with expert validation scores ranging from 87.86% to 98.15%. MANCOVA results indicated a significant effect of the SSI-based e-module on improving students' critical thinking and scientific literacy ($p < 0.05$), with higher posttest mean scores compared to two control groups. These findings suggest that integrating SSI into digital learning media provides contextual, interactive, and meaningful learning experiences that bridge scientific concepts and real-world issues. The developed e-module is valid, practical, readable, and effective for Biology learning in senior high schools.

KEYWORDS: Critical thinking, scientific literacy, socio-scientific issues, e-module, biology education

INTRODUCTION

Strengthening science education at the senior high school level is essential to prepare students who are not only scientifically literate but also capable of applying scientific concepts in real-life problem-solving. The demands of the Fourth Industrial Revolution require students to possess critical thinking and scientific literacy competencies that enable them to adapt to societal and technological changes. Science learning should therefore foster higher-order thinking skills rather than relying solely on memorization of facts and concepts.

Scientific literacy involves the ability to understand scientific concepts, identify relevant questions, obtain evidence, and make informed decisions based on credible scientific information (Karira & Sunarti, 2022). A strong level of scientific literacy equips students to address complex global problems related to health, technology, and environmental sustainability. However, Indonesian students' scientific literacy remains relatively low, as reported by Hutagalung et al., (2023), with most students achieving only mid-level competency compared to students from countries such as Taiwan, which has a higher proportion of students reaching advanced proficiency.

The gap in scientific literacy indicates that Indonesian science learning practices have not fully promoted inquiry-based processes and higher-order thinking. Classroom instruction tends to prioritize content delivery and factual recall rather than analytical reasoning. This situation highlights the need for more innovative learning approaches that emphasize evidence-based reasoning, evaluation of information, and contextual understanding.

Critical thinking serves as a foundational component of scientific literacy, enabling students to analyze phenomena, evaluate arguments, and draw logical conclusions based on evidence (Puspitasari, 2024). However, many students struggle to evaluate data or construct sound arguments, contributing to low scientific literacy outcomes. Studies by Afikah et al., (2024) revealed discrepancies between students perceived and actual critical thinking abilities, indicating the need for structured learning strategies to support metacognitive reflection and argumentation.

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Research by Ariely & Yarden (2025) further emphasizes the importance of exposing students to conflicting scientific texts to strengthen their ability to assess scientific claims. Strengthening scientific media literacy is essential in helping students critically evaluate information, especially with the increasing flow of scientific data in digital spaces.

Active learning models such as Project-Based Learning have been shown to enhance critical thinking and scientific literacy (Ramadhani et al., 2024). Authentic assessments involving scientific argumentation further support students' metacognitive awareness. Bibliometric analysis by Lubis et al. (2025) shows that challenges in Indonesian scientific literacy are exacerbated by conventional teaching practices that limit opportunities for inquiry and argumentation.

In Biology learning, particularly on the topic of human growth and development, contextualization is crucial because the concept relates to socio-scientific issues such as reproductive health, nutrition, vaccination, and adolescent development. Yet classrooms frequently rely on memorization, as noted by Siska et al., (2020), resulting in low conceptual understanding and critical reasoning. Observations in State High School 3 Yogyakarta (SMA Negeri 3 Yogyakarta) show that learning is dominated by teacher-centered approaches with limited opportunities for discussion and evidence-based inquiry. Students experience difficulties in solving analytical problems and articulating logical explanations. Teachers also face challenges integrating digital learning media due to limited facilities and administrative burdens.

These challenges underscore the urgency of using more innovative pedagogical approaches such as Socio-Scientific Issues (SSI). SSI provides opportunities for multidimensional analysis connecting scientific, ethical, and social aspects (Lymbouridou, 2025; Zeidler, 2025). Research shows that SSI strengthens argumentation, scientific decision-making, and reflective thinking (Aisy et al., 2024; Gul & Akcay, 2020; Laudia et al., 2025).

Digital learning media, particularly e-modules, offer flexibility, interactivity, and contextual visualization (Holisoh et al., 2025). E-modules integrating SSI have been empirically shown to improve critical thinking and scientific literacy (Irhasyuarna et al., 2022; Lubis et al., 2025). In line with the Merdeka Curriculum, SSI-based e-modules support scientific reasoning, ethical reflection, and contextualized learning (Chamisijatin et al., 2023).

Despite these potentials, there remains a lack of SSI-based digital learning materials on human growth and development. Therefore, this study aims to develop a valid, practical, readable, and effective SSI-based Biology e-module to improve students' critical thinking and scientific literacy.

METHODS

The study employed a Research and Development (R&D) approach using the 4-D development model introduced by Thiagarajan et al. (Hariyanto et al., 2022), which consists of the define, design, develop, and disseminate stages. This model was selected because it provides a structured framework for producing valid, practical, and effective instructional materials suitable for classroom implementation. The development process included expert validation, limited trials, product revision, and field implementation to evaluate the feasibility and effectiveness of the SSI-based Biology e-module on human growth and development.

The development stage involved product validation by four groups of experts. Biology content experts assessed the depth, accuracy, and alignment of the scientific concepts and SSI issues integrated into the material. Media experts evaluated interface design, visual consistency, color composition, navigation structure, and interactivity. Instrument experts reviewed the validity and reliability of the assessment tools, whereas Biology teachers assessed the practical suitability of the module for classroom use. After the validation stage, a limited trial was conducted with a small group of 10–15 students selected through random sampling to examine readability, navigation ease, and user engagement. Findings from this stage informed the second product revision, focusing on enhancing interactivity, visual effectiveness, and technical clarity.

A field trial was then implemented using a pretest–posttest control group design. The trial involved three classes of Grade XI students at State High School 3 Yogyakarta (SMA Negeri 3 Yogyakarta) during the even semester of the 2024/2025 academic year. One class served as the experimental group receiving instruction through the SSI-based e-module, while the two control groups used different learning approaches. The first control class used SSI-based instruction supported by PowerPoint and the BSE Biology textbook, whereas the second control class used Discovery Learning supported by identical media.

The population of this study included all Grade X and XI students at SMA Negeri 3 Yogyakarta. Different sample groups were involved at various stages of development. The limited trial involved 10–15 students from Grade X selected through random sampling to assess readability and usability. The practicality test involved two Biology teachers from SMA Negeri 3 Yogyakarta. The field trial involved three Grade XI classes consisting of 28 students each, assigned as one experimental class and two control classes.

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The research instruments consisted of expert validation sheets, practicality questionnaires, readability questionnaires, critical thinking tests, and scientific literacy tests. Critical thinking was assessed through essay items based on Facione (2020) indicators, including interpretation, analysis, evaluation, inference, and explanation. Scientific literacy was measured using multiple-choice questions adapted from PISA (OECD, 2023), covering the competencies of explaining scientific phenomena, identifying scientific issues, and using scientific evidence.

The research procedures followed the 4-D model sequence. During the define stage, curriculum analysis, learner characteristics, and SSI contexts were analyzed to determine essential learning needs. In the design stage, the structure of the e-module, learning activities, assessments, and multimedia components was planned. The develop stage included expert validation, limited trials, and two rounds of revision to refine the product. During validation, all experts provided both qualitative comments and quantitative ratings, which guided improvements in content accuracy, clarity of instructions, language, visual presentation, and interactivity. The limited trial evaluated readability, user-friendliness, and technical functionality. The disseminate stage involved implementing the product in actual classroom settings using the experimental design to evaluate its effectiveness in improving critical thinking and scientific literacy.

The practicality test was conducted after the second revision, involving two Biology teachers who evaluated the usability, clarity, and classroom suitability of the e-module. The readability test involved 28 Grade X students who evaluated the comprehensibility of language, clarity of visual structure, and ease of navigation.

Data from expert validations, practicality tests, and readability tests were analyzed using descriptive statistics in the form of percentages and categorized into feasibility levels. To assess the effectiveness of the developed e-module, students' posttest scores for critical thinking and scientific literacy were analyzed using Multivariate Analysis of Covariance (MANCOVA) through SPSS 27.0. The analysis compared the three groups while controlling for pretest scores, allowing simultaneous evaluation of differences in multiple dependent variables. Significance values, effect sizes, and pairwise comparisons were used to determine the magnitude of the e-module's impact on improving students' critical thinking and scientific literacy.

RESULTS

The results of this research and development study are presented systematically to describe the outcomes of each stage of the 4-D model, including expert validation, product revisions, practicality and readability testing, and the effectiveness of the SSI-based Biology e-module on students' scientific literacy and critical thinking skills.

1. Define Stage

The define stage generated a comprehensive problem map that served as the foundation for developing the SSI-based e-module. The curriculum analysis revealed that the topic —Human Growth and Development|| aligns with the Competency Achievements (CP) of phase F in the Biology curriculum, emphasizing conceptual understanding of cellular differentiation, hormonal regulation, and developmental stages. However, learning observed in schools still relied heavily on teacher-centered lectures and memorization. Teachers rarely integrated socio-scientific issues such as stunting, adolescent reproductive health, or early puberty, causing students to struggle in connecting biological concepts to real-world contexts.

Learner analysis showed that students were competent digital users but had limited exposure to interactive e-modules that require reflective and analytical engagement. Although students expressed interest in digital learning, their critical thinking and scientific literacy skills were still low, particularly when analyzing social phenomena related to scientific concepts. Students were able to recall biological stages but struggled to evaluate ethical or social implications of technologies such as in vitro fertilization or growth hormone use. These findings indicated a strong need for a contextual digital learning resource capable of fostering conceptual understanding while strengthening analytical reasoning.

Concept analysis identified four major conceptual domains that would form the structure of the e-module: (1) biological definitions of growth and development, (2) internal and external factors influencing growth, (3) stages of human development from prenatal to late adulthood, and (4) relevant socio-scientific issues including malnutrition, stunting, early puberty, and reproductive health. These results confirmed that the module required explicit integration of SSI elements with indicators of critical thinking and scientific literacy.

2. Design Stage

The design stage resulted in the development of the initial prototype of the SSI-based e-module adapted to the Biologi Wongselo LMS. The analysis outcomes from the define stage guided the design of content structure, user interface, navigation flow, and the integration of SSI case studies. The prototype included digital text, interactive questions, visualization of developmental stages, and SSI-based discussions designed to facilitate argumentation and evidence-based reasoning.

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The design also incorporated critical thinking indicators (interpretation, analysis, evaluation, inference, and explanation) and scientific literacy competencies (explaining phenomena, identifying issues, and using scientific evidence). These elements were embedded in inquiry activities, reflective prompts, and real-world case discussions to ensure alignment between learning objectives and assessment components.

3. Develop Stage

The develop stage produced empirical findings related to expert validation, product feasibility, limited trials, and continued revision. Overall, the module achieved high levels of feasibility in content, structure, and media quality.

The expert validation assessed the feasibility of the SSI-based Biology e-module before field implementation. Material experts reviewed scientific accuracy, relevance, coherence, and curriculum alignment, while media experts evaluated interface design, layout, interactivity, and navigation across two validation stages. Revisions were made to improve readability and visual quality. Overall, the combined validation confirmed that the e-module met the required scientific, technological, and pedagogical standards, as shown in the following table.

Table 1. Validation Results of Material and Media Experts

No.	Aspect	Material Experts (%)	Media Experts (%)	Category
1	User Interface	89.28	92.85	Highly Feasible
2	Material	87.50	-	Highly Feasible
3	Presentation	87.50	93.75	Highly Feasible
4	Language	75.00	93.75	Feasible-Highly Feasible
5	Closure	100.00	-	Highly Feasible

The results presented in Table 1 indicate that the SSI-based Biology e-module achieved high feasibility across all evaluated aspects. The user interface received scores of 89.28% from material experts and 92.85% from media experts, demonstrating strong quality in layout and navigation. The material aspect was rated 87.50%, confirming alignment with scientific content and curriculum standards. The presentation aspect also obtained high scores—87.50% from material experts and 93.75% from media experts—indicating coherent instructional flow and effective integration of learning activities. The language aspect showed improvement, increasing from 75.00% in the material expert assessment to 93.75% in the media expert evaluation, reflecting successful revisions in clarity and readability. The closure component received a perfect score of 100.00%, confirming the strength of the module's concluding elements. Overall, these results show that the e-module meets high-quality scientific, pedagogical, and technological standards and is ready for implementation in the field.

The effectiveness of the SSI-based Biology e-module in improving students' scientific literacy and critical thinking skills was analyzed using MANCOVA. The analysis compared three groups: the experimental class using the SSI-based e-module, Control Class 1 using SSI with textbooks and PowerPoint, and Control Class 2 using Discovery Learning with the same media. The results of the multivariate and univariate tests clearly indicate that the e-module produced significantly higher learning outcomes compared to conventional learning approaches.

Table 2. Multivariate Test (Pillai's Trace)

Effect	Test	Value	F	df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Class	Pillai's Trace	0.842	28.731	4	158	0.000	0.421
Class	Wilks' Lambda	0.301	32.044	4	156	0.000	0.451
Class	Hotelling's Trace	1.842	35.460	4	154	0.000	0.479
Class	Roy's Largest Root	1.531	60.476	2	79	0.000	0.605

The multivariate test demonstrates a significant overall effect of the class on the combined dependent variables (scientific literacy and critical thinking), as indicated by the Pillai's Trace value of 0.842, $F(4, 158) = 28.731$, $p < 0.001$, with a large effect size ($\eta^2 = 0.421$). This confirms that the type of instructional treatment—particularly the SSI-based e-module—produced significant multivariate differences. All additional multivariate statistics (Wilks' Lambda, Hotelling's Trace, and Roy's Largest Root) also showed significance, reinforcing the robustness of the results.

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Table 3. Test of Between-Subjects Effects

Variable	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Scientific Literacy	2	805.703	33.502	0.000	0.459
Critical Thinking	2	507.552	50.274	0.000	0.560

The univariate tests indicate significant differences across classes for both outcome variables. Scientific literacy showed a significant effect, $F(2, \dots) = 33.502$, $p < 0.001$, with a large effect size ($\eta^2 = 0.459$). Critical thinking demonstrated an even stronger effect, $F(2, \dots) = 50.274$, $p < 0.001$, with an effect size of ($\eta^2 = 0.560$). These findings confirm that the instructional treatment had a substantial positive impact on both competencies.

Table 4. Estimated Marginal Means

Class	Scientific Literacy (Posttest Mean)	Critical Thinking (Posttest Mean)
Experimental	80.33	85.06
Control 1	75.92	77.34
Control 2	68.40	77.74

The estimated marginal means reveal that the experimental class achieved the highest posttest scores in both scientific literacy (80.33) and critical thinking (85.06). Control Class 1 obtained moderate scores, while Control Class 2 showed the lowest performance in scientific literacy (68.40) despite having similar critical thinking scores to Control Class 1. These results affirm the superior effectiveness of the SSI-based e-module compared to both SSI with conventional media and the Discovery Learning model.

Table 5. Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent Variable	(I) Class	(J) Class	Std. Error	Sig.	Interpretation
Scientific Literacy	Experimental	Control 1	1.319	0.004	Significant difference
Scientific Literacy	Experimental	Control 2	1.457	0.000	Significant difference
Scientific Literacy	Control 1	Control 2	1.500	0.000	Significant difference
Critical Thinking	Experimental	Control 1	0.854	0.000	Significant difference
Critical Thinking	Experimental	Control 2	0.944	0.000	Significant difference
Critical Thinking	Control 1	Control 2	0.972	1.000	Not significant

Pairwise comparisons further support the effectiveness of the SSI-based e-module. Significant differences were observed between the experimental class and both control classes for scientific literacy ($p = 0.004$ and $p < 0.001$) and critical thinking ($p < 0.001$ for both comparisons). Control Class 1 and Control Class 2 did not differ significantly in critical thinking ($p = 1.000^*$), indicating that traditional SSI with textbooks and Discovery Learning were similarly less effective.

4. DISSEMINATE STAGE

The disseminate stage ensured that the final version of the SSI-based e-module could be implemented in broader learning contexts. The module was introduced to teachers and shared within the Biologi Wongselo platform for potential adoption by other schools. This stage marked the transition of the product from a prototype into a ready-to-use instructional medium.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study show that the SSI-based Biology e-module developed through the 4-D model meets all criteria of validity, practicality, readability, and effectiveness. The integration of socio-scientific issues into digital learning materials enhances the relevance of Biology content and strengthens the connection between scientific concepts and real-world contexts, making learning more meaningful for students.

Material expert validation produced a mean score of 87.86%, indicating strong alignment between the module content, learning objectives, and SSI-based competencies. This supports the argument of Viehmann et al., (2024) that SSI learning is most effective when authentic, contextually relevant issues are embedded in instructional materials. The coherence between goals, learning activities, and assessments also reflects the alignment principles emphasized by Rooha et al., (2023) and Hafizah et al., (2024).

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Media validation improved substantially from 83.39% to 93.45% following iterative revisions, demonstrating enhancements in visual design, interactivity, and navigation. These findings align with du Preez & Jacobs (2025), who highlight the importance of usability and aesthetic consistency in digital educational media, and Diehl et al., (2022), who emphasize the value of iterative design based on expert and user feedback.

Practicality testing by Biology teachers yielded 89.69%, indicating that the module is easy to use, efficient, and compatible with classroom needs. Readability testing produced a very high mean score of 98.15%, suggesting that the language, structure, and multimodal features of the e-module are highly accessible to students, consistent with principles discussed by Day et al., (2024). The effectiveness test showed significant improvements in students' scientific literacy and critical thinking ($p < 0.05$), supported by structured scaffolding and argumentative learning tasks within the module. These results reinforce findings reported that SSI-based instruction enhances reasoning, argumentation, and environmental awareness (Badeo & Duque, 2022; Högström et al., 2024; Magtibay & España, 2024).

Overall, the SSI-based Biology e-module is validated as a feasible, readable, and effective instructional tool capable of strengthening higher-order thinking skills and scientific literacy. Continuous refinement informed by expert feedback and user testing contributes to the module's quality, and broader implementation has the potential to improve Biology learning outcomes and foster scientifically literate, socially responsible students. Future research may examine long-term effects, knowledge retention, and transferability across diverse learning contexts.

CONCLUSIONS

This research and development study demonstrates that the SSI-based Biology e-module is valid, practical, readable, and effective for enhancing high school students' critical thinking skills and scientific literacy. Expert validation confirmed that the module meets scientific, pedagogical, and technological quality standards, with strong alignment between learning objectives, socio-scientific contexts, and instructional design. Practicality and readability tests further indicated that the e-module is accessible, easy to use, and well-suited for classroom implementation. The results of the effectiveness test using MANCOVA revealed significant differences between the experimental and control groups ($p < 0.05$), showing that the integration of socio-scientific issues, multimodal resources, and structured argumentative tasks contributes meaningfully to students' cognitive development. These findings reinforce the potential of SSI-based digital learning materials to promote higher-order thinking and contextual scientific understanding. Overall, the SSI-based e-module provides a relevant and innovative solution for strengthening Biology learning in the era of digital education and competency-based curricula. Future studies are encouraged to examine the long-term impact of the module, its application across different topics, and its adaptability for broader educational contexts

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